

THE STABILITY INVESTIGATION OF STIFFENED COMPOSITE FUSELAGE PANELS UNDER COMBINED PRESSURE AND COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

An experimental study is conducted to validate a finite element and numerical method for a stiffened composite fuselage panel with multiple stringers and frames under the different conditions. The configuration and dimension of stiffened composite panel and the experiment fixtures are designed for this test. And this paper established analysis process for a stiffened composite fuselage panel. The nonlinear finite element method (FEM) and test under axial compression, axial compression and airtight loads, damage tolerance and axial compression are successfully carried out. The strain gauges and the digital image correlation (DIC) equipment (non-contact strain measurement technique) are used and set on the specimens to detect the position and timing of damage occurring. The comparisons between experimental and numerical results of the buckling modes and loads, postbuckling deformations, and final failure loads indicate good agreements.

1 INTRODUCTION

As the aircraft fuselage panels withstand dramatic pressure and compressive loads, its compressive stability is an important concerned problem for researchers and designers. And the test is easy to failure. Most works mainly focus on the only compressive buckling and postbuckling behaviors of flat composite panels [1-3]. The stability of such panels, when subjected to compression or shear loads, is a primary design problem. With increasing use of composite materials in aircraft primary structures, the stability of stiffened composite panels has drawn close attention from the researchers and designers [4, 5]. Some researchers studied the compressive stability of curved composite panels. However, the researches on the stability of complex curved composite panels under combined pressure and compression are not sufficient. Experimental and numerical methods are used in this paper to investigate the compressive buckling and postbuckling behaviors of curved stiffened composite panels that are composed of seven Ω stringers and four frames. A 500T test machine and pressurizing fixture are used to apply compressive load and inner pressure on the composite panels. Meanwhile, the nonlinear finite element (FE) analysis using Riks method is carried out in this paper.

2 EXPERIMENT

The configuration and dimension of stiffened composite panel are shown in Fig.1. The skin, stringers and frames are all made of carbon/epoxy composite materials. The ply sequences of skin, frames and Ω stringers are $[\pm 45/0/0/+45/90/-45/0]_s$, $[\pm 45/0/0/90/0/0/\pm 45]_s$, and

$[\pm 45/90/\pm 45/0/0/\pm 45]_s$ respectively. The main dimensions of each part are given in Fig.2. There are three specimens in the experiment. They are of the same configuration and dimensions, except that discrete source damage is induced in the third one by cutting the middle stringer. The length of the cut is 180 mm in length, 5 mm in height.

Fig.1 Configuration and dimensions of curved stiffened composite panel

Fig.2 Configuration and dimensions of frame and Ω stringer

The mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy composite materials are listed in Table 1.

Elastic modulus / GPa	E_{11}	E_{22}	G_{12}	ν_{12}	-
	164	9.0	4.14	0.32	-
Failure strain / $\mu\epsilon$	ϵ_{11t}	ϵ_{11c}	ϵ_{22t}	ϵ_{22c}	$\gamma_{2\%}$
	15000	7900	10000	24000	12000

The experiment fixtures include two platens, a gasbag, a metal box, some beams and two pillars. The upper and lower platens are fixed to the test machine, and axial compressive load is applied on the specimen. The air is pumped into the gasbag to produce an inner pressure of 0.06 MPa. As the gasbag is surrounded by the fixed metal box, beams and specimen, the inner pressure is eventually applied on the specimen, as shown in Fig.3.

To take full advantage of experiment specimens, the stiffened composite panel is loaded to first buckling under different load cases before loaded to final failure in compression. Therefore, the stiffened composite panel is designed to be suitable for both the compressive and airtight load cases. The left and right sides of the skin are extended as the connection regions joined with the pillars. Two pieces of laminates are bonded at the connection regions front and back for reinforcement. The reinforced plates have the same lay-up as the skin. The

top and bottom ends are potted in aluminum potting boxes filled with resin, as shown in Fig.1. The loading faces of the boxes are machined flat to achieve uniform compressive load condition. By stabilizing the air pressure in the gasbag, the airtight loads are directly applied to inside surface of the specimen, as shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3 Experiment setup

Fig.4 DIC setup

The Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique is used to monitor the buckling mode with the load increasing in the experiment as shown in Fig.4. The strain gauges are used to record the strains on the skin and stringers.

The outer surface of the skin is painted white strewn with black spots as shown in Fig.3, which would be used to measure the displacements and strain fields of the skin by the DIC technique, as show in Fig.4. Meanwhile, the strain gages are placed on the skin and stringers. Five 0° strain gauges are bonded on each section of the hat stringers. The strain rosette gauges

are placed on the skin front and back. To make the measuring areas of DIC as continuous as possible, the front skin surfaces where painted white are free of any gauges.

Fig.5 The setting scheme of strain gauges

The compressive load is applied at a rate of 0.5kN/s until final failure. The strains and DIC photos are recorded in every increase of 1.0 kN. The sounds and damages in the experiment are recorded with digital videos for the analysis afterwards. The first specimen is tested under axial compressive load to study the compressive-only buckling and failure strength. The second specimen is tested under combined pressure and compressive load to study the inner pressure effect on the compressive buckling and failure strength. The third one is tested for the damage tolerance (DT) study under combined pressure and compressive load.

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The FE analysis is carried out in Abaqus. The specimens are modeled with S4 shell elements. The tie constraints are used to model the bonding between the skin and stringers, as shown in Fig.6. The bolted joints are simulated with combination of B31 beam elements and coupling elements. This model has more than 781 B31 beam elements.

Fig.6 also indicates the boundary and load of the stiffened panel that FEM adopted in the analysis. The supported end is completely fixed. The nodes of skin and Ω stringers in the pot are constrained in degree 3 of freedoms. A compressive force is applied to the top edge using MPC constraint. A pressure of 0.06 MPa is applied to the inner face of the specimen. A concentrated compressive force of 1500kN is applied on the loading end.

Fig.6 FEM

The geometrically nonlinear analysis associated with modified Riks method is carried out for the compressive buckling and postbuckling process of the stiffened composite panel. The Riks method discovers a single equilibrium path in a space defined by the displacement and loading parameters. It is generally used to predict unstable, geometrically nonlinear collapse of a structure. A very tight convergence tolerance is set to prevent the load floating back because of the existence of local buckling. The final failure is predicted by maximum strain criterion.

4 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Fig.7(a) shows the typical failure mode of curved stiffened composite panels under compression. Fig.7(b) shows the ultimate failure morphology of curved stiffened composite panels in DT test.

(a) Compression test

(b) DT test

Fig.7 Failure modes

Fig.8 shows the third specimen damage form of damage tolerance test and numerical analysis result.

(a) DT test

(b) Numerical

Fig.8 Damage form and numerical analysis of the third specimen

Fig.9 shows the deformation of the third specimen which is used for damage tolerance test under the 1760KN compression load and airtight load.

Fig.9 The deformation of the third specimen under 1760kN

Table 2 provides the buckling and failure loads of curved composite panels in experiment and numerical analysis. The buckling load in combined pressure and compression test is 4.7% lower than in compression test. Their ultimate failure loads are similar. The failure load of DT test is 18% lower than the second test. The error of predicted buckling load is less than 5.0%. The error of predicted failure load is less than 10.2%.

Table2 Experimental and numerical results of buckling and failure loads

	Experiment /kN		Numerical /kN	
	Buckling	Failure	Buckling	Failure
Spec.1	1940	2078	1900	2290
Spec.2	1850	2019	1920	2050
Spec.3	-	1761	-	1677

The compressive buckling and postbuckling behaviors of the aircraft fuselage panel with multiple stringers and frames are studied in this paper. The configuration and dimension of stiffened composite panel and the experiment fixtures are designed for this test. The DIC technique is used to monitor the deformation development of the skin at different load levels. The comparisons between experimental and numerical results of the buckling modes and loads, postbuckling deformations, and final failure loads indicate good agreements.

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